

THE PECULIARITIES OF TASK BASED INSTRUCTIONS TO IMPROVE SPEAKING SKILLS OF EFL STUDENTS THROUGH ROLE-PLAYS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7965380>

Abstract: The goals of this study are (1) to find out student's speaking skills before being taught by using task-based instructions. (2) To know changes and developments of the students' speaking skills after being taught by using task based instructions. (3) To find out major differences of students' speaking skills before and after the study.

In this study 15 second year students of Uzbekistan State World languages university participated. Their English level was B2 on average, but, they had many difficulties when it comes to speaking part. For this study, researcher interviewed students before the test and find out major problems. For main test, students participated in role plays 3 times. Finally, they were interviewed again, in order to know the effect of role play to develop their speaking skills.

Keywords: students' speaking skills, importance of role-plays,

Introduction.

English is one of the world's most important language. Almost everyone uses it to communicate, and they do so from many different nations. English has always attracted unique interest. It is because of the importance of English in any part of our lives. English language proficiency is crucial in international relations in order to engage in the larger work community. The speaking skill is measured in terms of the ability to carry out a conversation in the language.

In learning speaking skill, the students often find some problems. The problem frequently found is that their native languages causes them difficulties to use the foreign language. Other reason is because of motivation lack to practice the second language in daily conversation. They are also too shy and afraid to take part in the conversation. Many techniques can be applied including role play, because research findings say that this techniques is effective to use in teaching speaking, since they are more easy to use and more practical.

Teaching speaking by using task based instruction has many disadvantages, such as: it can enrich students' speaking skill, it can make teaching learning process becomes more comfortable, it can also help the students to speak English correctly. Beside advantages for students feel relaxed in accepting the lessons for using and speaking lesson. It can be implemented by using task based instruction technique as teaching instrument, for example using it as the helping tools to the students to use, speak and respond by using English correctly.

Literature review.

Hamouda (2012) from Qassim University Saudi Arabia conducted a study related to problems faced by students in speaking. The findings revealed that many students in EFL classrooms feeling reluctant to respond to their teacher due to many factors such as low English proficiency, fear of speaking in front of others, negative evaluation, shyness, lack of confidence and preparation, and fear of making mistakes. Similarly, EFL students feeling unwilling to speak English in Indonesia experience the same factors and cultural matter affects their

learning. The students tend to speak Bahasa Indonesia when they are learning English in class. They turn to be “unquestioning minds” in interaction as they believe that a teacher never makes mistakes (Marcellino, 2008). The cultural tendency of Indonesian in which people enjoy living in harmony creates the students’ minds and attitudes when learning (Suryanto, 2015). The students do not show great initiative in learning as they prefer to do what their teacher asks them to.

Task-based learning emphasizes the learning on the use of tasks both in planning teaching and classroom teaching (Richards, 2006; 30). The learning is focused on the negotiation of meaning, the use of target language for authentic and meaningful communication (Richards, 2006). Negotiation of meaning is aimed to resolve communication problems (Suzuki, 2018). Task-based learning accommodates the students to learn the use of form and communication (Larsen-Freeman & Anderson, 2011; 193). The form-focused work is functioned as the enabling skills since it is designed to develop skills and knowledge that will ultimately facilitate the process of authentic communication (Nunan, 2004: 22). The enabling skills are in two kinds: language exercises and communicative activities. The students are hoped to not only understand the language functions but also to use them (Branden, 2006; 6). The students are intended to improve linguistic accuracy in their speech although there are no communication problems between them (Suzuki, 2018). Since the concept of task-based learning is learning by doing, the students are expected to experience the language by completing the tasks.

The proponents of tasks-based learning mention types of tasks carried out during the learning process. Richards (2006) says that pedagogical tasks and real-world tasks facilitate the students to experience the language. Pedagogical tasks, for example information gaps, aim at the use of strategic interaction and the element of language (Nunan, 2004 in Khoshsiman & Tasuj, 2014). Meanwhile real-world task, for example, a role-play of an interview, reflects the use of language beyond the classroom. Pedagogical tasks are not designed for the students to practice performing the tasks but to activate the students’ speaking skills (Nunan, 2004). Willis and Willis (2007) suggest seven task types: ordering, sorting, matching, comparing, project and creative tasks, sharing personal experience, problem-solving, and listing. J. Willis (1996) says that task is a goal-oriented activity in which the students use language to achieve a real outcome. They use whatever target language resources they have in order to solve a problem, do a puzzle, play a game, or share and compare experiences.

Nunan (2004;35-37) provides principles in implementing task-based learning. They are (1) scaffolding in which lessons and materials should provide supporting the learning takes place and the students are not expected to produce language that they have not learned yet, (2) task dependency, that is within a lesson, one task should grow out of, and build upon, the ones that have gone before, (3) recycling language maximizes opportunities for learning and activates the ‘organic’ learning, (4). Active learning, learners learn best by actively using the language they are learning, (5) integration, learners should be taught in ways that make clear the relationships between linguistic form, communicative function and semantic meaning, (6) learners should be encouraged to move from reproductive to creative language use, (7) reflection, learners should be given opportunities to reflect on what they have learned and how well they are doing.

Role-play is a “complete range of communication technologies to develops language fluency, to promotes student interaction during the class, to increase students’ motivation, and to share responsibilities between teacher-students” (Kusnierek in Rojas Rojas, 2018). The students act different characters dan speak the language they learn. They plan the roles, choose the vocabularies, and the expression they need (Waffa, 2014 in Rojas & Villafuerte, 2018). The findings of a study conducted by Krebt (2017) show that there is a significant improvement in the speaking skill of the experimental group of students using role play. Dingli suggested a well-designed role play technique for the students to reflect and experience responsible learning (Dingli, Khalfey, & Leston-Bandeira, 2013).

Methodology.

Fifteen students are enrolled in this study. They are students of the English Department in second course in Uzbekistan State World languages university. Based on the results of an interview and observations to get the first data, it showed that the students had problems in speaking due to inadequate language knowledge and lack of confidence. Therefore, the researcher conducted this study in 3 steps:

Step1. Students were given a problematic topic to prepare a role play as a group and reminded of the language expression and vocabulary they needed to use to complete the task. In this stage, participants were given problematic situation at the market to prepare short role play together with adequate language expressions an enough topic related vocabularies. They did preparations during 4 days and presented ready role play in front of the class.

Step 2. In this part, students were told to be prepare for the role play, but this time they were not given any language expressions and vocabularies to use.

During this stage, students made aware that they should do role plays on the topic of divorce in a family one hour before the research start, but they did not provided neither language expressions, necessary grammatical rules nor topic related vocabularies.

Step 3. In this part, participants had no idea about what to do, even they were not told to do role plays.

On this stage, when participants came in the research room, they were told to prepare role play immediately without any preparations beforehand. This time they did this on the topic of “Problematic situation between student and teacher”.

Results.

Fifteen students participated in this study. They were interviewed for pre-test and post-test findings. The students were also evaluated at the beginning and at the end of the research to identify their speaking development on accuracy, vocabulary and comprehension.

At the beginning of the research, the vast majority of students have difficulty on speaking in terms of many aspects, which will be described on table below:

Problems with grammar	3 students
Fear of speaking in front of many people	5 students
Lack of vocabulary	2 students
Lack of ideas	4 students
Shyness	1

After all experiments, students shared their feelings about this research:

“After 3 role plays, I feel myself as an English native speaker, because, now I am not facing with fear in front of other people, I have less fear than before now”

“I felt great development with my speaking skill. Before I had fear, depression lack of ideas, and my speaking was so boring because of lack of intonation and feelings. But, after experiencing 3 types of role plays, now, my speaking is totally changed. Now, I even can speak without beforehand preparation, which was my big problem before”

“My speaking was not that much bad actually, but after 3 role plays to develop my speaking skill was very very useful. Despite my speaking was good, I had a problem was with finding ideas, now, I can speak without preparations beforehand.”

Discussion

The improvement of students speaking skills takes place in each stage during the action in class. The students seem to increase their confidence as they carry out the speaking activities step by step.

The students` test results in three cycles reveal that the students improve their speaking skills significantly. A slight improvement from the mean score in stage 1 indicates that the students started speaking appropriately. The students were trained to be aware and to get used of applying appropriate grammar and vocabulary when speaking.

The students seemed struggling and not confident at the beginning, but they enjoyed during the study. The students learned to speak even without beforehand preparation. The students seemed much confident to play different roles and topics in stage 2 and 3. Variety of topics used for conducting role-play may help the students improve their vocabulary(Krebt, 207)

Conclusion.

Importance of task based instructions to develop speaking skills of EFL students is very paramount thing. It has identified that, through task-based instructions students can develop their public speaking skills, can erase their fear of speaking as well as they can develop their confidence at speaking. At the end of this survey, all participants experienced improvement on their speaking skills.

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